

**FOOD, HEALTH AND ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES
TO TACKLE EMERGING PRIORITIES**

Deliverable 1.5

Report on communication and outreach activities (RP1)

Technical References

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Introduction

Deliverable 1.5 provides the opportunity to report on the communication and outreach activities within the FHERITALE project in the first reporting period (Jan 2024-June 2025). During this time following the beginning of the project, Instruct-ERIC, in their capacity as WP1 leads responsible for core communication and outreach activities, and project partners have contributed to a range of activities that have driven awareness of the project.

The project's communication plan set out in D1.4, contains 4 major objectives:

- Establish a project website to inform general public about goals and achievements of the project
- Outreach and communication activities of the FHERITALE project outcomes to all relevant stakeholders
- Implementation of a portfolio of activities to manage and monitor internal and external communication of FHERITALE to all stakeholders with the aim of explaining the ambition and objectives of the project in a consistent manner
- Outreach activities including specific events organised within the frame of FHERITALE as well as engagement in third-party events (ICRI, ERIC Forum, HE projects)

In order to progress towards these objectives, we have targeted the following actions

1. Raise awareness of the FHERITALE consortium and its activities;
2. Increase the broader life science community's understanding of the involvement of RIs in the study of artificial materials and their impact on food, health, and the environment;
3. Ensure adherence to FHERITALE branding and establish a clear consistent style;
4. Create a central catalogue space on the website of relevant services and technologies
5. Regularly evaluate the impacts of the various communication channels and tools used.

This deliverable also serves as the basis for continued communication efforts in the second reporting period. Both the activities outlined above, and those performed during RP2, will be monitored and evaluated by the project's Ethics Advisor.

1. Raising awareness of the FHERITALE consortium and its activities

In addition to the [FHERITALE website](#), which is hosted by Instruct-ERIC via the ARIA platform (an RI management tool provided by Instruct-ERIC), FHERITALE is active on two different social media platforms, LinkedIn and Bluesky. Although X was used to provide updates on the project and developments related to the research fields of potential stakeholders, the subsequent movement of many scientists to alternative platforms made the consortium decide that it was no longer a suitable platform for actively posting to. The project retains a presence on the platform should the situation change in the future, but for now does not actively post to X.

a) Project website

The FHERITALE website was set up early in June 2024, and in the year leading up to this report has been visited 1295* times, with 8524* page views (* indicates these figures are correct as of the time of writing in June 2025). As expected, the most popular page is the FHERITALE home page, with 3949* views, however other pages have also received a high number of views, including publications (479*), webinar 1 (407*), and survey outcomes (359*). A breakdown of the pages viewed can be found in Table 1 below. Figure 1 shows a spike in visits to the FHERITALE website was seen during the registration for Webinar 1 (December 2024) and following the webinar itself and the release of its recording (January 2025), demonstrating the importance of such dissemination events for bringing traffic to the FHERITALE website. As outlined in the Communication Plan (D1.4), the website is the fundamental communication resource for the FHERITALE project, acting as the central hub of information. All communication activity outlined in this report directs users to the FHERITALE website to find more details and resources.

Page name	Number of views
Homepage	3949
Publications	479
Webinar 1	407
Survey Outcomes	359
White Paper	273
March 2025 Newsletter	246

Table 1: Breakdown of views per page

Figure 1: Breakdown of page views between June 2024 and June 2025

Over the course of RP1, a number of pages on the website have been updated with new information relevant to the project. For example, following the strategic retreat in Utrecht in October 2024, and following the first FHERITALE webinar in January 2025, the website home page was updated to provide information on these events. Moreover, as the project has progressed a number of key outcomes have been displayed on the website, including the summary of services available to researchers in Europe who work to understand the impact of artificial materials on food, health, and the environment, as well as the FHERITALE white paper. Ten news items to date have been published on the FHERITALE website, covering a variety of project updates, and events. There have also been updates to the publications section of the website, with cutting-edge articles relevant to the project area communicated to website visitors through this page. The publications are broken down into three sections, and are regularly updated to highlight relevant and engaging publications (Figure 2).

Figure 2: The Publications page on the FHERITALE website

<p>FHERITALE 76 followers 5mo · 🌐</p> <p>Join Us for an Exclusive Webinar: The Impact of Nano- and Microplastics on Health, Food, and Environment: A Glance at Current Research.</p> <p>Learn more about the goals of the FHERITALE project and hear from expert speakers examples of studies on the impact of micro- and nanoplastics.</p> <p>📅 Date: 16/01/25</p> <p>🕒 Time: 11:00-12:15 CET</p> <p>📍 Where: Microsoft Teams</p> <p>👤 Expert speakers:</p> <p>Silvia Orlandini (ICAR) Alba Hernandez (Plasticheal) + 1 more TBC!</p> <p>Register today! https://lnkd.in/eV9tkkKd</p> <p>FHERITALE</p> <p>WEBINAR: The Impact of Nano- and Microplastics on Health, Food, and Environment: A Glance at Current Research</p> <p>Learn more about the goals of the FHERITALE project and hear from expert speakers examples of studies on the impact of micro- and nanoplastics.</p>	<p>Advertisement including flier for the first FHERITALE webinar.</p>	<p>400</p>	<p>3.25%</p>
<p>FHERITALE 76 followers 1mo · 🌐</p> <p>📄 Micro and Nanoparticles Research: Priorities, challenges, and recommendations.</p> <p>A white paper prepared by members of the #FHERITALE consortium highlights critical challenges in the current understanding of micro and nanoparticles, including inconsistent use of terminology, lack of reference materials, and gaps in risk assessment.</p> <p>We also outline a number of key short-term and long-term recommendations to address these issues, such as development of more sensitive analytical techniques, providing funding opportunities for researcher training, and research on mitigating the release of nanoplastics to the environment.</p> <p>Explore the full white paper to better understand the challenges for this growing area of research, and our recommendations to combat them.</p> <p>#Microplastics #nanoplastics #EnvironmentalResearch</p>	<p>Report on the white paper prepared by members of the FHERITALE consortium on challenges and recommendations in MNP research. The engagement rate is particularly notable.</p>	<p>333</p>	<p>54.95%</p>

Table 2: Breakdown of best performing LinkedIn posts and their engagement

Bluesky

Set up in November 2024, the initial aim of the FHERITALE Bluesky account was to utilise the rising number of scientists migrating from X to Bluesky to increase the following of the project. This aim was met successfully via ensuring the FHERITALE account was present in several ‘starter packs’ available to users new to the platform, who could then follow all accounts in a starter pack that they were interested in, for example, “microplastics research”. The co-ordination team at CERM/CIRMMP were instrumental to this and the success the project is seeing on this platform. The FHERITALE account currently has 301 followers on Bluesky, and regularly posts short-form updates relating to the project, or more frequently, updates from the literature to remain engaged with the community. In addition to this, and as is the case for LinkedIn, the platform is a useful way to network and interact with parallel initiatives to grow the reach of the project.

Since being set up, the FHERITALE bluesky account has posted 63 times (an example of a post is shown in Figure 3). Detailed analytics pertaining to the impressions these posts have on followers and other users are not yet available, as Bluesky develops further. Content primarily focused on publications that were added to the website, events such as the first FHERITALE webinar, and requests for input on the survey.

Figure 3: Successful post on the FHERITALE Bluesky account, highlighting the upcoming first webinar.

Publication of Project results

FHERITALE has a dedicated workspace on Zenodo for all project public documents to be uploaded and shared ([FHERITALE Zenodo Community](https://zenodo.org/communities/fheritale)). To date, the most frequently viewed and downloaded is the White Paper “Key Selected Priorities: Micro and Nanoparticles Research: Priorities, Challenges and Recommendations” (<https://zenodo.org/records/15222316>), viewed and downloaded 74 times.

In addition to the resources available on Zenodo, a scientific publication presenting the landscaping and the bibliometric analysis conducted within the WP4 activities has been published in the Open Research Europe (ORE) platform (<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.20244.1>).

c) Events

Presentations and Talks at In-Person Events

Partners including Instruct-ERIC and Sciensano have presented FHERITALE at several conferences and in-person events in RP1, providing a snapshot of FHERITALE, and inviting interested partners in the audience to find out more about the project after the talk. The full list of meetings and symposia in which this talk was presented can be found below:

- Instruct-SI Minisymposium, Ljubljana, May 2024
- Instruct Centre Forum, Cascais, May 2024
- FEBS Conference, Milan, June 2024
- Instruct-EL Symposium, Athens, October 2024
- Instruct-LV Minisymposium, Riga, December 2024
- Instruct-ERIC Managers Meeting, Grenoble, April 2025
- Instruct-NL Symposium, Utrecht, May 2024
- Sciensano Chemical Friday Pitch Session, December 2024

Figure 4. FHERITALE presented by Instruct-ERIC at the Instruct-NL Symposium, held in Utrecht May 2025.

Poster Presentations and Discussions at In-Person Events

In addition to talks, the FHERITALE project was presented as posters at several European events in RP1, providing the opportunity to talk directly with researchers interested in hearing more about micro- and nanoplastic research infrastructure. The list of conferences and meetings in which a poster was presented, or where FHERITALE was discussed, is shown below:

- Poster presentation of FHERITALE by Instruct at Instruct Biennial Structural Biology Conference 2024, Cascais, May 2024
- Meeting between CNB-CSIC representatives and SusPlast platform for identification of new services/technologies, October 2024
- Workshop Plastiche & ambiente, Ravenna (IT), June 2025

Online Meetings

FHERITALE has also been represented at several online events. Online events are a highly efficient way to get across impactful material without overuse of resources. Similarly, webinars provide the opportunity to send links and resources directly to a captive audience through chat channels, directing them to relevant content and materials on the FHERITALE website. A key example of this is the first FHERITALE Webinar, which took place in January 2025 (Figure 4). Organised by the FHERITALE project internally, it ensured that the speakers, audience, branding, and therefore messaging, could be kept to what FHERITALE needed. Utilising the webinar function of Teams from Instruct-ERIC, the webinar had three speakers outlining their work on food, health, and environmental research in the context of micro- and nanoplastics.

Additionally, FHERITALE was represented at the RI-Hubs webinar on Science Diplomacy. The webinar was attended by representatives in both Europe and Latin America, covering the role that science can play in solving thematic problems, including food, health, and environmental challenges. The role of the FHERITALE project was acknowledged in the webinar, and distributed to participants.

- Webinar 1
- ERIC Forum Annual Meetings
- RI-Hubs Webinar on Science Diplomacy

Figure 5. The first FHERITALE webinar, January 2025.

The other significant benefit of online meetings is that, with permission of all speakers, they can be recorded and used as further dissemination. The first FHERITALE webinar, for example, was uploaded to the Instruct-ERIC YouTube channel, where it has been viewed more than 170 times. This is a) more than initially attended the webinar, and b) provides a platform for the long-term viewing of the webinar.

Newsletters

The first FHERITALE newsletter was published and distributed in March 2025, outlining project updates and upcoming initiatives. FHERITALE partners AnaEE and Instruct-ERIC both shared updates from the FHERITALE project in their newsletters. AnaEE shared updates in Feb 2024, October 2024, Jan 2025, and June 2025, where the map of services was shared. Instruct-ERIC highlighted the FHERITALE kick off meeting to their community in their June 2024 newsletter.

2. Increasing the broader life science community's understanding of the involvement of RIs in the study of artificial materials and their impact on food, health, and the environment

One of the main goals of this work package is to shed light on the resources available through RIs that can be made available to life science researchers in Europe to understand the impact that artificial materials are having within a One-Health perspective. During the first 6-9 months of the project, where information gathering within WP1 and WP3 was essential for the delivery of a survey for services offered by research infrastructures, and for defining the thematic priorities of the project, social media posts highlighting the work of partners, and publications relevant to the project were used to engage with the wider community.

In particular, the aforementioned survey was a critical means to engage with other RIs as the questionnaire was advertised both through the ERIC Forum and through direct contacts via e-mails. Several RIs responded positively and were further involved in related project activities. For instance, EMBRC and Euro-BioImaging representatives accepted to be an external advisor for the FHERITALE project and participated in the Strategic retreat meeting (Milestone 5) held in Utrecht on October 14-15 2024, facilitating the discussion on potential synergies and future collaborations.

As the project has progressed, more avenues of communication have been uncovered. In March 2025 the first FHERITALE newsletter was published on LinkedIn and on the FHERITALE website for download. The newsletter provided background context to the project goals and the consortium, as well as a first update on the availability of services for researching the impact of artificial materials through European Research Infrastructures. A second newsletter highlighting updates from the project is due to be shared at the end of June 2025.

Another key route to engaging with the existing communities of life science researchers in Europe to raise awareness of the project and the resources available to researchers is to interact with other projects with existing communities. To this end, the first FHERITALE webinar, with speakers from Plasticheal (Alba Hernandez, project co-ordinator) as well as from members of the PRIORITY COST action (Gabriela Kalčíková, Planterastics group leader) was a good way to interact with these existing communities. The webinar, and information about the project itself, was also featured on the CUSP cluster website, as well as through their social media channels, each with 100s of followers. As a result of this, and our own dissemination efforts and through project partners, we saw great interest in the webinar, with 143 registrations, and 116 attendees on the day. This clearly highlighted that webinars are a great way to engage with new communities, and work to set up future, more regular webinars, has continued within this period with the goal of hosting several more in the Autumn of 2025, which will be used to disseminate further project updates.

3. Ensure adherence to FHERITALE branding and establish a clear consistent style

A key aspect of the FHERITALE Communication Plan was to maintain a consistent brand identity. This has been achieved with focus in three main areas:

- a) Logo
- b) Website content and style
- c) Physical dissemination materials

Ensuring that these three aspects are aligned in their branding, style, tone of voice, and overall objective was key to maintaining a consistent identity for FHERITALE in the first reporting period.

a) Logo

The FHERITALE logo was designed at the outset of the project by CERM, and was agreed and formalised by the project consortium. One of the central mechanisms for consistent brand identity is to ensure that the logo is clear, visible, and identifiable. As a result, all FHERITALE communications include the logo.

The logo is the fundamental aspect of the project’s branding, and can be deployed in its master setting with a white background, but also as a white version for coloured backgrounds, ensuring it fits into a variety of graphics and communication materials. An example of both forms of the logo can be found in Figure 6.

Figure 6. FHERITALE light and dark backgrounds (left and right respectively) in their content environments.

b) Website Content and Style

The FHERITALE website sets the tone for branding throughout the remainder of the project. The colours of the navigation menus, graphics, and buttons match that of the logo. All graphics designed for the website, such as the map of all partners (Figure 7) include the logo, and the correct colours for FHERITALE. Graphics designed for external platforms, such as

social media include the logo, colours, and font but also the website URL, social media handles, and contact addresses where appropriate, ensuring that users can engage with the project and get in touch with the coordinators.

Figure 7 outlines another feature of the FHERITALE website that is consistent and utilised in other graphics: the background header image. This image (polymers associated with plastics) was selected to be the image introducing all major pages on the site and has been included in several other materials, such as both graphics displayed in Figure 6.

Figure 7. The FHERITALE homepage, including the background “polymer” image in the header.

c) Physical Dissemination Materials

FHERITALE has developed a small number of printed flyers which were provided to partners for their own dissemination activities. The aim of the flyers was for partners to distribute them as they visit conferences, meetings, and events in which they will promote the project. The flyers provide an overview of the project, the project partners, relevant links to get more information, and contact details.

4. Central catalogue space on the website

The map of available RI services for food, health, and environmental research, with a focus on micro- and nanoplastics, has been added to the website as part of Deliverable 3.1. The map is available to view and access on the website homepage, but also is available in the resources section (Figure 8), and as a news item, reflecting its position as a major output of the project so far. The map of services will be continually updated as the project progresses and additional service providers fill in the survey

As the FHERITALE website is built using the ARIA SiteBuilder, the website, and therefore survey results, are guaranteed to remain beyond the project’s own lifespan, ensuring that resources provided continue to be accessible into the future.

Figure 8. The Resources section of the FHERITALE website, showing outputs and key resources from the project.

5. Regularly evaluate the impacts of the various communication channels and tools used

Statistics for the website are collected by Matomo, a GDPR-compliant website analytics tool which enables the identification of impactful communication activities, e.g. the first FHERITALE webinar, which caused a significant spike in website traffic (shown in Figure 1).

Analytics tools for Bluesky are not yet available, but should that change in the future then this will enable us to analyse the impact of posts on this platform in greater detail to further hone our strategy for communicating through the platform. For LinkedIn, analytics are available for the last 365 days, allowing analysis of the engagement rate with posts and the impressions. Posts that performed well in this area are highlighted in table 2.